
УДК 004.738.5:330.341.1:005.3

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IMPLEMENTATION OF ORGANIZATIONAL INNOVATIONS IN AN IT-COMPANY USING THE ADKAR CHANGE MANAGEMENT MODEL

The article examines the implementation of organizational innovations in an IT company using the ADKAR change management model, which is a structured algorithm for the adoption of innovations by employees. Innovations provide the company with the opportunity to be competitive in the market. Organizational innovations adjust processes within the company, helping to build and sustain a strong work performance culture. The purpose of the article is to disseminate knowledge and awareness of the need for change management in the modern dynamic environment, with a particular focus on human resources. In the world of information technology and remote work, there is a pressing need of building a structured mechanism for work management and delivering effective outcomes. Additionally, the article discusses the advantages and disadvantages of the ADKAR model which supports change processes, considering the size of the company and the professional field it applies to. As a conclusion to the article, “best practices” of implementing the ADKAR model are provided, using the example of a hypothetical IT company. The company’s management aimed to introduce organizational innovation – a new application for project managers daily work. Furthermore, it is proven in the article that implementing organizational innovations is necessary to maintain productivity and competitiveness, and are demonstrated – the effectiveness and practicality of the ADKAR, showing that the process of adopting to changes in the team went smoothly and without resistance.

Key words: organizational innovations, information technology (IT), changes, change management, change management methodologies, ADKAR model.

Кравивна Ксенія, Іванова Ольга. Впровадження організаційних інновацій в ІТ-компанії за використання моделі управління змінами ADKAR.

В статті розглянуто впровадження організаційних інновацій в ІТ-компанії за використання моделі управління змінами ADKAR, що являє собою структурований алгоритм дій для прийняття інновацій працівниками. Інновації надають можливість компанії проявити себе конкурентноспроможною на

ринку. Організаційні інновації налаштовують процеси всередині компанії, що допомагає побудувати та підтримувати міцну культуру виконання роботи. Метою статті є поширення знань та усвідомлення про необхідність управління змінами в сучасному мінливому середовищі з особливим фокусом на людські ресурси. У світі інформаційних технологій та віддаленої роботи постає гостра необхідність побудови структурованого механізму ведення роботи та надання ефективних результатів. Додатково, в статті розглядаються переваги та недоліки моделі ADKAR, що підтримує процес змін, враховуючи розмір компанії та професійну галузь, до якої вона застосовується. Наведено «найкращі практики» впровадження моделі ADKAR на прикладі умовної ІТ-компанії. Керівництво компанії спрямувало свої зусилля на впровадження організаційної інновації – нового застосування для щоденної роботи менеджерів проєктів. Більше того, в статті доведено, що впровадження організаційних інновацій є необхідним для підтримання продуктивності та конкурентоспроможності, а також продемонстровано ефективність та практичність моделі ADKAR, за допомогою якої процес адаптації до змін в роботі колективу відбувся плавно та без супротиву зі сторони працівників.

Ключові слова: організаційні інновації, інформаційні технології (ІТ), зміни, управління змінами, методології управління змінами, модель ADKAR.

Innovations are an integral component of the modern IT world, significantly impacting society and business. Innovations transcend the boundaries of science, technology, economics, and culture, altering our way of life and interactions with one another. Innovations in the company include the implementation of new ideas, concepts, products, processes, or approaches aimed at improving efficiency, business competitiveness, and creating new opportunities. There are various types of innovations, such as product, process, marketing, organizational, technological, and social innovations. The rapid adaptation of employees to professional changes is currently a relevant issue in a dynamic environment. The article explores the implementation of organizational innovations in IT companies using the ADKAR change management model, which is a structured algorithm for employees to accept changes.

Organizational innovations are a broad concept that includes several elements. In contemporary conditions, when most people work remotely from different parts of the world, with insufficient communication and work planning, organizational innovations are extremely necessary.

Innovations in organizing working time involve the use of time management tools, new concepts of activity structuring, and new methods of distributing responsibilities and authorities [3]. Organizational innovations impact people by changing the usual work culture [6]. Most modern change management methodologies are focused on working and interacting with people [8]. One such methodology is ADKAR model – a change management methodology that emphasizes the importance of creating positive incentives for accepting changes, providing necessary knowledge and skills to employees, developing their abilities, and offering support and reinforcement [10, 13]. It consists of five key elements: Awareness, Desire, Knowledge, Ability, and Reinforcement.

There are plenty of benefits to using the ADKAR model:

- The ADKAR model can be used both in small and big companies. It can also be used on individual level.

- The model focuses on people's needs and behavioural patterns.

- The model provides a practical approach that can be applied immediately.

- It is an out-of-the-box solution. This makes ADKAR an excellent choice for companies that want ready-made recipes for change.

- It has been extensively field-tested. ADKAR is one of the most popular and widely used change models, a testament to its success [14,15].

The ADKAR model will not work in the following cases:

- Since the model is ready-made and can be applied instantly it doesn't provide you with micro-level details.

- Company need is to develop more sophisticated, complex change management processes. When a company wants or needs to design a different process for change, they will likely need to explore other options.

- Company is making certain types of business changes. A company undergoing digital transformation, for instance, may be adopting multiple technologies simultaneously. In such cases, companies may need to draw on expertise from digital transformation agencies, digital adoption solutions, IT consultancies, and so on.

- Company has a different value system or culture. Some businesses may have a cultural mismatch with the Prosci system. In that case, it would only make sense to look at different change models [14,15].

The first step of the model is to create “Awareness” of the need for change. It is considered “successfully achieved” when the employee understands why changes are necessary, accepts them, and can assess the risks of refusing changes. The change initiator must prepare clear answers to the following questions and provide significant evidence [10]:

- Why are the changes necessary?
- Why are the changes happening now?
- What is wrong with what we are doing today?
- What will happen if we do not implement the changes?

It should be noted that resistance from employees at the “Awareness” stage is a completely normal reaction and should exist to support the balance of the work environment. In the book “Adaptation-Innovation,” author Dr. Michael J. Kirton emphasizes two cognitive styles of business managers on a spectrum from more adaptive to more innovative. Employees exhibit similar behavior: “Adapters are more ready to anticipate challenges and threats from the system (often develop timely plans for savings, reduction, etc.), while innovators are more ready to anticipate events that may attract or threaten from outside, such as early signs of changes in tastes and markets or significant advancements in technologies that have not yet been fully utilized” [12]. This quote shows an individual’s approach to external events. The fundamental question to initiate the adaptation process is “What’s in it for me (WIIFM)?” The change initiator explains the benefit of innovations for each group of employees, creating desire.

“Desire,” in the context of the ADKAR model, represents a crucial psychological component in the change management process. This element has two main driving forces: motivation and ultimate personal choice. “Desire” connects “Awareness” with the subsequent stages of the model, serving as a motivational catalyst that encourages individuals and organizations towards successful change implementation. At the core of the “Desire” element is the fundamental question: “Why do we need to change?”. To answer this question, it is extremely important to understand the benefits that the proposed change will bring and communicate them. However, to create more persuasive communication strategies, it is important to consider the following factors [10]:

- The nature of the change and «What’s in it for me?»;

- Organizational or environmental context;
- Personal situation of the individual;
- Internal motivation.

The organizational context and environment reflect how an individual perceives the environment that may change: the success of past changes, support, organizational culture, organizational direction, etc. Additionally, desire can be viewed through the lens of motivational psychology. Theories of intrinsic and extrinsic motivation come into play when people are guided by their internal desires for personal growth, self-realization, and purpose. The “Desire” element is closely intertwined with effective change management. Leaders must not only articulate a clear vision of change but also inspire and engage their teams or stakeholders. Support, understanding, and resistance-handling skills are essential for leaders to prepare employees for change.

The third element of the ADKAR model – “Knowledge” – shows how to implement changes. Effective knowledge dissemination strategies are essential at this stage, as the thinking of the employee or the organization as a whole is transformed. Such strategies may include training programs, seminars, informational materials, and online resources. Moreover, a scientific approach to “Knowledge” underscores the importance of pedagogical methods that cater to different learning styles and preferences, thereby providing motivation. Understanding new roles and responsibilities associated with changes is also crucial in preparing educational materials [10]. Additionally, it is important to evaluate the effectiveness of training. Scientific approaches, such as knowledge assessments and quizzes, can be used to determine the level of understanding and retention of relevant information by individuals. This allows identifying knowledge gaps and adjusting corresponding educational approaches accordingly. Acquiring knowledge is a necessary prerequisite for developing the skills and competencies needed for the successful implementation of changes.

The fourth element of the ADKAR model – “Ability” – helps develop the competence of employees to effectively implement an initiative and achieve the desired level of productivity. Several factors influence an individual’s ability to adapt to changes [10]:

- Psychological barriers;

- Physical capabilities;
- Intellectual abilities;
- Time available for developing necessary skills;
- Availability of resources for developing new abilities.

Psychological barriers paralyze individuals and hinder their actions. For example, the fear of public speaking. Then manager or change lead should provide trainings to develop presenting skills. The most crucial factor is time. In the modern world, people strive to master new technologies in extremely short periods to be among the first and gain the most advantages. People and businesses need clearly and sensibly defined timeframes for learning, awareness, testing, and reinforcing skills and knowledge. Another essential factor is the availability of resources to support development, such as training sessions, seminars, practical sessions, coaching, mentoring programs, finances, necessary tools, and materials, which can sometimes be challenging to obtain and may require additional time, and which should be planned during «Knowledge» step.

The «Ability» element of the ADKAR model is a stage where knowledge transforms into practical competence, which subsequently requires «Reinforcement». The fifth element of the model includes the implementation of measures and strategies to ensure the sustainability of recently acquired behavioral, procedural, or systemic changes introduced during the initiative. The purpose of this stage is to prevent the loss of progress from the previous four steps, i.e., to preserve the integration of changes in the organization in the long term [10]. From the perspective of behavioral psychology, people tend to revert to familiar practices even after acquiring the knowledge and skills for development. In the «Reinforcement» phase, the following strategies are employed to ensure the stability of changes:

1. Feedback and Evaluation: Regular impact assessments and feedback mechanisms help identify any deviations or areas that require additional attention.
2. Recognition and Rewards for individuals and teams that embrace changes and consistently adhere to new practices. Incentives can motivate and reinforce desired behavior.
3. Leadership and Role Modeling: Leaders play a crucial role in

reinforcing changes by setting an example through their actions and behavior. Continuous support and commitment to the initiative are essential factors.

4. Integration into Organizational Culture: Changes should be embedded in the values, beliefs, and daily practices of the organization. They should become a part of the organizational culture.

To analyze the effectiveness of the ADKAR methodology, the author of the article chose a hypothetical IT company (the actual name of the company cannot be disclosed for data protection), whose goal was to implement a unified automated project management application. The first attempt incurred losses of approximately \$30,000, lasted for 6 months, and only 80 out of the planned 200 employees were able to master the application. Upon reviewing the project implementation plan, the change initiator realized that there was a lack of clear awareness of the change and communication, as well as insufficient employee support. It was decided to use the ADKAR methodology, following each step clearly.

The following were created:

- A website to announce the problem, the change's purpose, and the benefits for each employee (creating "Awareness" and "Desire").
- Material base for acquiring necessary skills and knowledge for working with the new application (links to short videos introducing the principles and steps of using the application; organizing 2 training sessions for all new users: one for basic knowledge and one for advanced topics, etc.).
- Support service for inquiries about using the application and a group of champions who helped demonstrate the application's benefits.
- Weekly online meetings for discussing issues, announcements, and knowledge dissemination.
- Monthly meetings with the company's management department, as managers demonstrated how they used the application and motivated subordinates.

These actions led to effective results. For comparison, the number of users by the end of June 2023 was 80 individuals, and by the end of October 2023, it had increased to 170 individuals.

Proved that modern opportunities to use effective change management methods and methodologies allow implementing the process of innovation

with maximum efficiency. The need to develop a culture that encourages taking calculated risks stimulates innovation, and innovation is growth, competitiveness, and success. For the maximum effectiveness of change implementation, it is advisable to communicate openly, explain the necessity, provide access to training and support during the active phase of changes, identify the benefits of innovation implementation for each employee group, inform them, and create a system of recognition and rewards for employees.

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